

THE SHARE OF ISLAMIC BANKS IN EUROPEAN COUNTRIES

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Annotation: Islamic financial system based on religion emerged in some Muslim countries in the 1970s. The aim of the Islamic financial system is to promote a smooth circulation of funds between the funds and investors, just as in the traditional system. However, the distinguishing aspect of the Islamic financial system is that it is based on sharia principles, which are the religious law of Muslims. First of all, the factors that should contribute to the development are indicated. Then the problems faced by the Islamic banking industry in the European Union will be analyzed. In this article, opinions and comments will be made about the share of Islamic banks in European countries.

Keywords: European countries, Islamic Bank, development, revenue growth, financial system, investors.

With the share of Islamic financial institutions in total assets of nearly 80 per cent, Islamic banks play a dominant role in the Islamic financial industry. They operate in more than 75 countries, not only Muslims, but also in countries where few Muslims live. It is an analysis of the opportunities and challenges of Islamic Bank development in EU countries. The analysis should answer the question of whether Islamic banks will be able to participate in the European financial market in the future more important than now. The article consists of four parts, not counting the introductory and final words. In the first part of the article, a descriptive analysis of the basic principles of Sharia, which affect the activities of Islamic banks. They include: interest (riba), avoidance of ambiguity (cave) and Prohibition of trading with illegal (dirty) products. Due to the need to adhere to these principles, the tools offered by Islamic banks should be structured differently from traditional ones.

The comparison between Islamic financial instruments and conventional institutions is amazing. In fact, Islamic finance is at the center of several recent studies conducted in Europe, in particular by the European Commission and the European Central Bank, in which the problems and opportunities of a sharia-compliant financial system are highlighted.

First, unlike those encountered in the traditional financial system, empirical evidence on the risks associated with Islamic finance has revealed that Islamic financing is less than half as dangerous as traditional financing. Other issues are efficiency and profitability, stability and stability of Islamic institutions. In this

regard, studies conducted before the economic crisis did not find meaningful differences between Islamic and traditional banks in terms of efficiency, while recent data, including studies, suggest that during the crisis, Islamic banks had more difficulties in maintaining the same level of profitability as traditional banks.

It shows that the Islamic Bank in the countries of the European Union is at a very early stage of its development. Even in the UK, where Europe is the leader in Islamic finance, the assets of Islamic banks account for less than 1% of the total assets of the British banking sector. However, there is a potential for the development of the Islamic banking market in the European Union, which is mainly attributed to the large and growing population of Muslims in Europe. In addition, after the global financial crisis, which has seriously affected the European banking industry, there is a high demand for moral investment among Europeans, which can lead to an increase in the demand for Islamic financial services. On the other hand, there are still many problems facing the Islamic banking industry in the European Union, which cannot be easily solved.

These include: lack of relevant legislation in most European Union countries, especially on tax and control issues, problems with risk management, high prices of Islamic banking products and hostility to Islam, thus Islamic banking activities in European Society.

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